

FRAGILITY ANALYSIS FOR BALLISTIC DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Effective structural design to resist ballistic effects such as small arms or fragmenting weapons has been a goal since weapons were developed. Approaches currently in use for ballistic design are predominantly deterministic and allow designers to decide what wall thickness should be used to stop a prescribed projectile impacting at a predefined velocity. The research presented in this paper provides a framework for conducting reliability analysis of structures subjected to bullet and fragment demands. Thus, pseudo-fragility curves are developed for the limit states related to spall and perforation of wall panels, residual velocities of bullets and fragments, and injury to personnel. The pseudo-fragility analysis provides engineers and owners with a tool to quickly assess the reliability of a wall system subjected to high velocity, low mass projectiles. In particular, the proposed analysis method allows designers and owners to determine the probability of spall and perforation, residual velocity, and injury as a function of wall thickness or threat standoff distance.

KEYWORDS

Concrete; Ballistics; Penetration; Fragment; Probability; Fragility; Injury

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Abbreviations:

Cumulative distribution function (CDF): Gives the probability that a stochastic variable "X", with a proper probability density function, is equal to or less than a value (x).

Coefficient of variation (COV): The quotient of the standard deviation and the mean

1 INTRODUCTION

Reliability analysis and performance based design are becoming common practice in structural engineering as the occupant safety and building efficiency continue to become more important. The use of the fragility analysis method, which was originally developed in earthquake engineering (Cornell & Krawinkler 2000, Luco & Cornell 2000, Vamvatsikos & Dolsek 2011, Akiyama, Frangopol, Matsuzaki 2011, Karamlou & Bocchini 2015), has been expanded to other structural engineering fields including wind design (Petrini & Ciampoli 2010) and blast design (Olmati, Trasborg, Naito, & Bontempi 2015, Shi & Stewart 2015). The fragility analysis allows designers to quickly assess the probability of exceedance of limit states for structural components knowing the probability density function of the intensity measure. This paper develops a framework to expand the fragility analysis to the field of ballistic design allowing the designer to assess the probability of personnel injury for a given direct fire or indirect fire weapon, e.g. mortar round.

Effective structural design to resist ballistic effects such as small arms or fragmenting weapons has been a goal since weapons were developed. Approaches currently in use for ballistic design are predominantly deterministic, allowing designers to decide what wall thickness should be used in order to stop a prescribed bullet impacting at a predefined velocity. Cumulative distribution functions (CDF) have been obtained, see e.g. (Elek & Jaramaz 2009), for the mass dispersion of a fragmenting weapon, allowing a designer to set a confidence level for the mass of the fragment (DoD 2008a). Additional methods and algorithms have been developed for fragmenting munitions (DoD 2009). Current methods fall short of allowing the designer or owner to have an accurate understanding of the level of safety that is provided by a given design. To overcome this shortfall a probabilistic approach is developed that can be used in order to determine the degree of safety of a structural design against bullets and fragments. The proposed approach expands on reliability based analysis for fragmentation effects and penetration of fragments into concrete (Twisdale, Sues, & Lavelle 1993), allowing the designer to account for variability in the materials used, the construction thicknesses, the variation in the fragment size, distribution and strike velocity, and the probability of critically harming an inhabitant of the structure.

The approach is broken down into three categories: 1) Direct Fire Weapons, 2) Indirect Fire Weapons, and 3) Injury to Personnel. Category 1 introduces the concept of uncertainty in demand and capacity through stochastic variables utilized in bullet penetration equations. Category 2 expands on category 1 by introducing variables that are a function of the defined stochastic variables. Category 3 builds on category 2 by utilizing the output obtained in category 2 to determine the likelihood of personnel injury.

Each mentioned category is illustrated through numerical examples of a wall design in order to

assess: a) Threat levels presented in Unified Facilities Criteria (UFC) 4-023-07 (DoD 2008b), b) Typical mortar round approximated by a fragmenting cylindrical charge, c) Critical organ damage provided in UFC 3-340-02 (DoD 2008a).

2 MODELS FOR PERFORATION

The following sections list the threat parameters and relevant equations utilized in the performed probabilistic analysis. For each of the chosen submodels, other options are available in the literature. Readers and analysts are encouraged to explore other submodels besides the ones selected in this paper that may be more appropriate for their specific application. The goal of this manuscript is to illustrate a general framework in which various classes of submodels are integrated to assess pseudo-fragility curves for ballistic analysis.

2.1 Direct Fire Weapons

The UFC 4-023-07 provides design procedures for structures subject to direct weapons fire (DoD 2008b). Four different threat levels are defined to represent the weapons that can be expected to be used on a building and personnel. These threat levels were derived from the Underwriters Laboratories Standard for Safety (UL 752, UL 2005). The mentioned four threat levels are defined by the mass, impact velocity, size and shape of the ammunition. The parameters of interest for the purpose of this study are shown in Table 1; in particular the Underwriters Laboratories provides the nose performance coefficient, N , for the prescribed ammunition. Alternatively N can be calculated as the summation of 0.72 and a quarter of the quotient of the projectile nose length and diameter (DoD 2008b). Bullet mass is commonly calculated in grains, thus for consistency, bullet and fragment mass will be referred to in grains (15.43grain = 1g).

Design Basis Threat	UL 752 Level	N	Mass (grain)	Strike Velocity (m/s)	Diameter (mm)
Very High	10	1.31	709.5	856-942	12.95
High	9	1.39	166	828-910	7.82
Medium	5	1.26	150	838-922	7.82
Low	3	0.91	240	411-453	11.18

Note: "N" is the nose performance coefficient

The maximum penetration into an air backed concrete wall (mm), i.e. a wall without any backing material such as soil or sand, is empirically provided in Equation (1) where d is the projectile diameter (mm), m is the projectile mass (kg), c is the maximum gravel size in concrete (mm), assumed to be 19mm for most concrete (DoD 2008b), v_s is the strike velocity (m/s), f_c is the concrete compression strength (MPa), and f_{age} is the concrete age factor (taken to be 1). Note, many perforation/penetration equations exist, many of

which could be applied to create a fragility analysis. The aim of this paper is not to select the "best" penetration model as this is subject to debate and there is no model generally accepted as "best", but rather to select a well-known equation for penetration that can demonstrate the approach for a fragility analysis. Equation (1) is then utilized to determine the thickness required (mm) in order to prevent perforation, T_{PL} , in the empirically formed Equation (2) which can be used to calculate the residual velocity, v_r , of the projectile (m/s) in Equation (3) where t is the actual wall thickness (mm) of the panel.

$$P_c = \frac{56.6 \left(\frac{m}{d^3}\right)^{0.075} N m v_s^{1.8}}{d^2 \sqrt{f_c}} \left(\frac{d}{c}\right)^{0.15} f_{age} + d \quad (1)$$

$$T_{PL} = D \left[1.239 \left(\frac{P_c}{d}\right) + 1.132 \right] \quad (2)$$

$$v_r = v_s \left(1 - \frac{t/D}{T_{PL}/D} \right)^{0.733} \quad (3)$$

2.2 Indirect Fire Weapons

Upon detonation of a mortar, fragments are generated both from the mortar casing, termed "primary fragments", and from objects that interact with the blast wave generated from the detonation, termed "secondary fragments". In this paper, only "primary fragments" will be discussed and thus the name is shortened to fragment for convenience. Table 2 provides three different threat levels for indirect fire weapons. Unlike the direct fire threat parameters given in Table 1, the indirect fire weapon threat levels are defined relative to the protection provided and the proximity of the detonation; consequently the size of the fragmenting munition is dependent on the needs of the owner.

Design Basis Threat	Impact Distance (m)
High	Near Contact
Medium	2
Low	5

Once the mortar casing ruptures, a large number of fragments are generated which are assumed to all project with the same initial velocity. The most prevalent technique to determine the initial velocity, v_o (fps), is the Gurney method (Gurney 1943) shown in Equation (4); which is only valid for cylindrical cylinders uniformly packed with explosive, W (lbf) is the charge weight, W_c (lbf) is the weight of the

casing (the mortar in this case) and $(2E')^{1/2}$ (fps) is the Gurney Energy Constant dependent on the explosive type. Although it is assumed that all fragments have the same initial velocity, the strike velocities will differ as it is a function of the fragment mass, drag, and standoff distance. Note that the equations in this section were developed for English units; however, the results have been converted to SI units.

$$v_o = (2E')^{1/2} \left(\frac{W/W_c}{1 + 0.5W/W_c} \right)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

Numerous CDFs have been developed for the mass dispersion of fragments (Elek & Jaramaz 2009). CDFs give the probability that a stochastic variable "X", with a proper probability density function, is equal to or less than a value (x). There are numerous distribution laws available that are used to describe a real distribution of the high explosive projectile fragments, one of the classics is the Generalized Mott Distribution (Elek & Jaramaz 2009), shown in Equation (5) where $N_T(m)$ is the number of fragments greater than mass m , μ is the mean mass, and λ is an exponent depending on the thickness of the casing. The Generalized Mott Distribution is formulated based on three-dimensional fragmentation geometric statistics. For thin-walled steel casings, a value of $1/2$ for λ was found to be adequate (Arnold & Rottenkolber 2008).

$$N_T(m) = \exp \left[- (m/\mu)^\lambda \right] \quad (5)$$

The mean fragment mass is taken to be M_A^2 where M_A (oz^{1/2}) is the fragment distribution factor provided in Equation (6) (DoD 2008a). The fragment distribution factor is a function of the casing thickness t_c (in), the mean inner casing diameter d_i (in) and an explosive constant, B (oz^{1/2}·in^{-7/6}), dependent on the explosive type.

$$M_A = B t_c^{5/6} d_i^{1/3} \left(1 + t_c/d_i \right) \quad (6)$$

In order to determine the fragment diameter, a fragment shape as shown in Figure 1 is assumed. The caliber density, D (lb/in³), which is equal to the quotient of the fragment mass and the cube of the fragment diameter, is taken to be 0.079 grain/mm³. This defines a typical fragment shape of chunky geometry (DoD 2008a).

Figure 1: Standard fragment shape (DoD 2008a)

Many equations exist to calculate the penetration of a bullet or other designed projectile into concrete; however, there are relatively few equations available for fragment penetration in particular. The Modified National Defense Research Committee formula (NDRC 1946), originally derived by Beth (Beth 1946), was chosen because it agrees with the largest range of experimental test data (Kennedy 1975, Yankelevsky 1997), it is based on a theory of penetration with empirically determined coefficients allowing it to be extrapolated beyond the range of available test data with greater confidence (Kennedy 1975), it is one of the most representative equations in use (Li, Reid, Wen, & Telford 2005), and it is one of the only equations aside from the Amman and Whitney Formula (Kennedy 1975) available for fragment penetration. Additionally, empirical formulas have been developed for spalling and perforation limits based on the NDRC equation (Li, Reid, & Ahmad-Zaidi 2006). The Modified NDRC equation is reproduced as Equation (7) where X_f (in) is the maximum penetration of an armor piercing fragment into air backed concrete with a strength of 27.6MPa, d (in) is the diameter of the fragment and v_s (fps) is the strike velocity. The penetration depth can be adjusted for various concrete and fragment strengths (DoD 2008a). Equation (8) and Equation (9) provide the minimum thicknesses of the concrete wall to prevent perforation, T_{pf} (in), and spall, T_{sp} (in) respectively. The residual velocity of a fragment that perforates the concrete wall is empirically given by Equation (10). The penetration equations selected have been developed with empirically determined coefficients and are validated with experimental data based on standard quasi-static concrete cylinder strength, thus it is unnecessary to include dynamic increase factors for material strengths.

$$X_f = 2.86 * 10^{-3} d^{1.1} v_s^{0.9} \text{ for } X_f \leq 2d \quad (7)$$

$$X_f = 2.04 * 10^{-6} d^{1.2} v_s^{1.8} + d \text{ for } X_f > 2d$$

$$T_{pf} = 1.13 X_f d^{0.1} + 1.311d \quad (8)$$

$$T_{sp} = 1.215X_f d^{0.1} + 2.12d \quad (9)$$

$$v_r = v_s \left[1 - \left(\frac{t}{T_{pf}} \right)^2 \right]^{0.555} \quad \text{for } X_f \leq 2d$$

$$v_r = v_s \left[1 - \left(\frac{t}{T_{pf}} \right)^2 \right]^{0.555} \quad \text{for } X_f > 2d \quad (10)$$

While no methods exist for calculating the probability of obtaining a penetration depth given a bullet impact, a method has been established for fragment strikes. A confidence level, C_L , as defined by (DoD 2008a) where the probability that the weight of the fragment, m , is the largest weight fragment released, can be chosen to limit the design mass of the fragment as given in Equation (11).

$$m = M_A^2 \ln^2(1 - C_L) \quad (11)$$

The C_L is a one-sided confidence limit, giving the lower critical value of the CDF. For example, the engineer would select a C_L of 0.9 in order to design for a fragment that is 90% heavier than all the other fragments produced during the detonation. Unfortunately, the method provided in (DoD 2008a) does not account for the fragment trajectory. Instead, the method presented in this paper serves as a suitable probabilistic approach that allows the designer to determine the probability of a fragment to strike a target and assess the probability of injury to personnel, considering also uncertainties and trajectory of the fragments.

2.3 Injury to Personnel

Human organ tolerance levels have been established for four critical organs as defined in (DoD 2008a): thorax, abdomen, limbs, and head. Table 3 provides the threshold limit of each critical organ in terms of fragment mass and velocity. Intuitively, a fragment with a smaller mass must travel faster in order to cause bodily harm. Note that the threshold limit for each organ is not at a constant kinetic energy limit.

Critical Organ	Mass [grain]	Velocity [m/s]
Thorax	>17500	3.1
	700	24.4
	7	121.9
Abdomen and limbs	>42000	3.1
	700	22.9
	7	167.6

Head	>56000	3.1
	700	30.5
	7	137.2

3 THEORY AND CALCULATION

The following sections provide the distributions, mean values, and coefficients of variation utilized in the probabilistic analysis. The number of samples, n , was selected to be 100,000 for each input variable to ensure convergence. Figure 2 depicts a sample convergence plot for the probability of exceeding a residual velocity of 700m/s for a 150mm thick concrete wall for a ballistic threat level of "Very High". Similar results have been obtained for other cases, leading to the choice of 100,000 for the sampling size.

Figure 2: Sample convergence plot

Each group of random samples comprising the input variable was generated from a prescribed probability density distribution. The input variable is a variable which is independent of all other variables, while variables that depend on input variables are referred to as intermediary variables. To develop the distribution of an intermediary variable, Monte Carlo simulations were conducted utilizing the equations provided in the "Models for perforation" section. The Monte Carlo simulation assesses the probability of a certain event occurring through the repetition of a large number of deterministic experiments. In general, the Monte Carlo simulation is performed in four tasks as shown in Figure 3:

1. Statistic characterization of the random variables,
2. Generation of the samples from the prescribed probability density functions,

3. Solution of the deterministic problem for each set of inputs to compute a set of outputs,
4. Post-processing and statistical analysis of the results in order to obtain the probabilistic characteristics of the output variables.

Figure 3 generally depicts how the Monte Carlo process was utilized for the direct fire weapons, indirect fire weapons, and injury to personnel sections. To reduce computational time, variance reduction techniques such as a Latin hypercube combined with importance sampling could be applied; however, such techniques were deemed unnecessary for this application because computational expense was minimal.

In contrast to the Monte Carlo simulation, the confidence level method is unable to account for variations in input and thus intermediary variables as shown in Figure 3. The confidence level approach allows the engineer to design for one specific fragment mass, determined based on the corresponding mass value determined from the Mott Distribution from the confidence level selected, as provided in Equation (11). All other variables in the confidence level approach are considered deterministic, including the standoff distance and charge size. A probabilistic curve may be developed using the confidence level method by repeating the process and saving each calculated output value corresponding to the selected confidence level. Note, that all distribution parameters provided are in terms of the associated normal distribution; however, when calculating the reader must convert to logarithmic mean and logarithmic standard deviation using the appropriate probabilistic relationships (Ang, & Tang 2007).

Figure 3: Monte Carlo simulation versus confidence level method

3.1 Direct Fire Weapons

The bullet mean strike velocity for each threat level was taken to be the mean between the maximum and minimum allowable strike velocities for each threat level provided in Table 1. The Coefficient of variation (COV) of bullet strike velocity, defined as the quotient of the standard deviation and the mean value of the distribution, was selected such that the number of bullets with a strike velocity outside of the range provided in Table 1 was less than 1% of the total number of samples.

The distribution for strike velocity shown in Figure 4 was assumed to be lognormal for two

reasons. First, it guarantees that the variable takes only positive values, as it should be in this case. Second, the threat categories are created on the basis of experimental tests in which the bullet velocity must be within a range of values. If the bullet strike velocity falls outside this range, the test is void. Therefore, the chosen distribution accounts for the fact that technician aim for a strike velocity in the middle of the range in order to increase the likelihood of a valid test. The fact that bullet velocities are substantially smaller for the case of low threat depends on the customary way in which the threat levels are specified.

Figure 4: Strike velocity distribution

Similar to the bullet velocity, the bullet mass distribution was assumed to be lognormal with a mean value obtained from the mass expected for each bullet type used in the threat levels of Table 1. An open distribution report by the U.S. Air Force Academy found that the largest COV of bullet mass from a sample of 40 boxes of ammunition representing seven different companies was 0.0047 (Magee, Oats, & Courtney 2012). This COV is small enough to consider the bullet mass to be deterministic without causing any significant change in the results; however, the bullet mass is kept stochastic to demonstrate the flexibility of the methodology presented and in the event that the technique is used for weapons with more rudimental projectiles, with more uncertainty on the bullet mass. Some studies have shown that the concrete compressive strength may be well represented by a random variable with Gaussian distribution (e.g., Shimizu et al. 2000). However, in this paper it is modeled as a stochastic variable with lognormal distribution and a COV of 0.18 following the work of Enright & Frangopol (1998), which guarantees that this random variable takes only positive values, as required by the physical problem at hand. The purpose of this paper is to present a general methodology and, within this framework, analysts can use the particular distribution they find most appropriate. Table 4 provides a list of the stochastic variables, all of which are lognormal, with their mean values and coefficients of variation. The nose coefficient, N , bullet

diameter, d , and the concrete aggregate size, c , were taken as deterministic where c was assumed to be 19mm (DoD 2008b). In order to calculate residual velocities, a wall thickness with a mean of 150mm was assumed as provided in Table 4. The COV of the wall panel thickness was based on tolerances for precast concrete (PCI 2010).

Variable	Mean Value	COV
Very High Threat Velocity	899 m/s	0.015
Very High Threat Mass	709.5 grain	0.0047
High Threat Velocity	869 m/s	0.014
High Threat Mass	166.0 grain	0.0047
Medium Threat Velocity	880 m/s	0.014
Medium Threat Mass	150.0 grain	0.0047
Low Threat Velocity	432 m/s	0.015
Low Threat Mass	240.0 grain	0.0047
Concrete Strength	28 MPa	0.180
Wall Thickness	150 mm	0.001

3.2 Indirect Fire Weapons

Mean values for the explosive casing thickness and inner diameter were based on a typical cylindrical explosive (DoD 2008a), while the casing length was selected based on the 81MM M821 high explosive cartridge (American Ordnance LLC 2009). Precision for manufacturing mortars was assumed to be the same as that for bullets (Magee, et al. 2012), thus the same standard deviation was selected for the casing thickness, inner diameter, and length. The casing and charge mass were then determined through calculated volumes and known material densities, taking the casing material as mild steel and the explosive type as Composition B, which agreed with both the application in UFC 3-340-02 (DoD 2008a) and the mortar round developed by American Ordnance LLC (2009).

The Mott Distribution was formulated using Equation (5) and the fragment distribution factor provided in Equation (6). The CDF of the fragment mass for the Mott Distribution is shown in Figure 5. Additionally from the relationship between the caliber density to fragment weight and diameter, the fragment diameter distribution is determined as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: CDF of fragment mass and PDF of fragment diameter distribution

A mean standoff distance of 12m with a lognormal distribution and COV of 0.1 was chosen. The mean standoff distance was selected based on conventional construction standoff distances for load bearing, reinforced concrete walls of a high occupancy house (DoD 2012), where the required minimum standoff distance is 26m. The standoff distance is less than that of the required minimum standoff distance because it is assumed that the assailant would be firing an explosive round over a controlled perimeter from the required minimum standoff distance. The landing point is assumed to have a high degree of uncertainty, as aggressors often fire indirect weapons from significant distances, over obstacles without a clear line of sight to the target (DoD 2008c). Thus, although the assumption that the aggressor is firing from the required minimum standoff distance may be conservative, a coefficient of variation of 0.1 accounts for incompetence or firing from larger distances. It is important to note that while the 12 m standoff is a potential impact location, it is chosen purely for illustration purposes.

As the initial conditions (i.e. the initial velocity, v_o , a stochastic variable developed from Equation (4), and taking the initial time to be zero), forces acting on the fragment (i.e. gravity and drag), and standoff distance (stochastic variable with assumed lognormal distribution) are known, the trajectory and strike velocity of the fragment can be calculated. The initial launch angle, φ , for each fragment was taken as a uniformly distributed variable between -90° and 90° . Additionally, the direction of launch, θ , was taken as a uniformly distributed variable between 0° and 360° . The drag force was taken as a vector acting in the direction opposite of motion, It was determined by assuming a circular cross section using the corresponding fragment diameter from the fragment diameter distribution, and calculating the instantaneous drag coefficient as a function of the velocity as shown in Figure 6 (Zaker 1975). Note that although fragment shapes vary and are likely not to be circular, because area is the only factor correlated to shape that would change the strike velocity, different shapes are already taken into account by treating

the diameter of the fragment as stochastic. The equation of motion was then solved numerically using an explicit time stepping method (Chopra 2007). Once the strike velocity was calculated, a histogram of the fragment strike velocity for various mass bins was plotted as shown in Figure 7. Mass bins were selected based on the mass distribution CDF, with each bin representing 25% of the total mass. The center of each histogram bar is connected by a line as shown by the "Mass < Bottom 25%" bin in order to increase the plot visibility. As shown in Figure 7, there are a large number of low mass and low velocity fragments that will not have the kinetic energy required to penetrate any protective barrier.

Note that for indirect fire weapons, fragments initially accelerate more slowly than the explosive gases and then, due to greater momentum, eventually travel faster than the wave front and often arrive at the target first (Neff 1998). Therefore, it is possible that the air density could vary as the projectile travels and it may differ from the ambient air density. In these computations, such event is disregarded, and it is assumed ambient sea-level air density. Thus, this assumption introduces an approximation.

Figure 6: Drag coefficient versus fragment velocity (Zaker 1975)

Figure 7: Histogram of fragment velocity for various mass bins

The CDF provided in Figure 5 was for every fragment generated from the ruptured mortar casing; however, only a fraction of these fragments will actually strike the wall panel, depending on the trajectory of the fragment as well as the width and height of the wall panel (Zaker 1975). Figure 8 depicts the influence of the fragment trajectory and wall area on the probability of striking the panel. The wall panel width and height are taken as stochastic variables with COVs based on tolerances for precast concrete (PCI 2010). The mean width and height are based on standard precast concrete panel sizes currently used in industry (PCI 2010). Considering the likelihood of the fragment striking the wall panel a histogram can be plotted for the fragment as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 8: Variables dictating fragment trajectory

Figure 9: Histogram of fragment velocity for various mass bins for fragments that hit the target

Table 5 provides a list of the stochastic variables with their distribution type, mean values, and coefficients of variation. The concrete strength and wall thickness are the same as that utilized in the direct fire weapons analysis provided in Table 4. COVs of the weapons and structure are so small with respect to the COVs of the fragments, concrete strength, and standoff distance that in this case they are treated as deterministic.

Variable	Distribution Type	Mean Value	COV
Casing Thickness	Lognormal	12.7 mm	0.0004*
Casing Inner Diameter	Lognormal	304.8 mm	0.0004*
Casing Length	Lognormal	609.6 mm	0.0002*
Fragment Mass	Mott	75.9 grain	2.226
Standoff Distance	Lognormal	12.2 m	0.1000
Wall Width	Lognormal	12.2 m	0.0010
Wall Height	Lognormal	9.1 m	0.0010
Concrete Strength	Lognormal	28 MPa	0.1800
Wall Thickness	Lognormal	150 mm	0.0010

*COV is small enough to treat as deterministic for the analysis

3.3 Injury to Personnel

The critical human organ survivability thresholds provided in Table 3 are plotted in Figure 10 below. Fragments with a mass and velocity landing in the area above any of the threshold lines represent a threat to the organ for which it lies above. Since the thresholds for the various critical organs are very close to one another, a single threshold line based on the minimum of all three lines at any point was formed in order to simplify the analysis. Therefore, if a fragment lies above the single threshold line, it is assumed

that it will cause injury to all of the critical organs as shown in Figure 10. By taking the quotient of the quantity of fragments in the injury area and the total number of fragments, the probability of injury is obtained.

Figure 10: Critical human organ damage thresholds

Curves are developed providing the probability of injury versus wall thickness for the standoff distances provided in Table 2. In order to develop each curve, Monte Carlo simulations are conducted for each fragment to determine the mass and residual velocity of each of the n number of fragments for a given wall thickness and standoff distance, as shown in Figure 3. Thus, a single point on the probability of injury curve is calculated for each prescribed wall thickness and standoff distance. This process is repeated as shown in Figure 11 until the probability of injury versus wall thickness for each standoff distance is determined.

Figure 11: Schematic of the pseudo-fragility curve for injury

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following sections provide the results obtained through the Monte Carlo simulation and the intellectual merit of the study, presented through "pseudo-fragility curves". Usually, "fragility curves" are functions of an intensity measure, an interface variable introduced to fully represent the characteristics of the hazard with a single scalar (or sometimes vector) variable. However, in the case of ballistic threat, a general consensus on the most appropriate scalar intensity measure has not been achieved; therefore the curves presented in this paper are defined as functions of the wall thickness or the residual velocity, rather than the ballistic demand, hence the name "pseudo-fragility curves".

4.1 Direct Fire Weapons

Pseudo-fragility curves are developed for the limit state of perforation as a function of a prescribed threat level where the wall thickness serves as the intensity measure as shown by the solid lines against the primary abscissa in Figure 12. The developed pseudo-fragilities can act as a design tool for the engineer to quickly determine what wall thickness is required to achieve a particular level of safety. For example, to stop a bullet from perforating a wall 80% of the time, a 300mm thick wall would be necessary to achieve a medium threat level, while a 500mm thick wall would be necessary for a very high threat level. Additionally, the designer can use the curve to assess the probability of perforation for a given wall thickness. For example, for a 500mm thick wall, there is an 80% probability that a very high threat level will perforate the wall.

Curves are also developed for the probability of exceeding a particular residual velocity for a given wall thickness (in this case a mean wall thickness of 150mm) as shown by the dotted lines against the secondary abscissa in Figure 12. For example, it is very unlikely that the bullet corresponding to a low threat level will penetrate a 150mm thick wall with a residual velocity of at least 200 m/s, while there is approximately a 50% chance for a medium threat level bullet and a 100% chance for a very high threat level bullet.

Figure 12: Probability of perforation and exceeding a given residual velocity for various threat levels

Residual velocities can also be plotted for the case of multiple wall thicknesses. Figure 13 depicts the pseudo-fragility curves for a very high threat level where residual velocity is the intensity measure at four different wall thicknesses. Intuitively, a bullet is less likely to perforate a thicker wall panel with a particular minimum residual velocity. Note for the case of no wall, the residual velocity pseudo-fragility is directly determined from the distribution of the strike velocity.

Figure 13: Probability of exceeding a given residual velocity for various wall thicknesses for a very high threat

4.2 Indirect Fire Weapons

Similar to the direct fire weapons' probabilistic analysis, the pseudo-fragility of a fragment perforating a wall can be plotted with the wall thickness as the intensity measure. Figure 14 provides the probability of spall or perforation occurring for a mean standoff distance of 12m for all fragments on the primary

ordinate and for fragments that strike the wall panel on the secondary ordinate. As seen by considering the fragment trajectory, even with an infinitesimally thin wall panel the probability of spall or perforation is not 100%. This is attributed to the possibility that the fragment may not strike the wall panel at all.

Figure 14: Fragment perforation and spall probability for a mean standoff of 12m

The Monte Carlo results were compared to the confidence level method of (DoD 2008a) by following the process laid out in Figure 3. A numerical program was developed in order to plot multiple confidence level points versus wall thicknesses. As shown in Figure 15, the pseudo-fragility analysis (by Monte Carlo simulations) leads to a significant difference from the confidence level method. Differences between the confidence level method and the pseudo-fragility analysis are attributed to the compounding of the many stochastic variables and the numerical determination of the fragment strike velocity which could not be implemented in the confidence level method. The fragility method accounts for aspects of the physical problem that are not captured by the confidence interval method, such as the trajectory.

Figure 15: Pseudo-fragility method versus confidence level method for a mean standoff of 12m

Furthermore, as the standoff distance is decreased, the confidence level method and pseudo-fragility analysis begin to converge for all wall thicknesses. This is due to the fact that at small standoff distances, less than 6.1m (DoD 2008a), the fragment strike velocity will be approximately equal to the initial velocity, regardless of the fragment mass or drag. However, the confidence level method is unable to account for the actual probability of fragment strike due to fragment trajectory (initial launch angle and direction) and wall area and thus may lead to more conservative results.

A sensitivity study was conducted on five different parameters to determine their influence on the final results. The sensitivity study was conducted for the specific case of probability of perforation of a 100mm thick wall due to fragments from an indirect fire weapon. In each sensitivity study all variables except for the variable in question are kept the same as the original analysis. For example, in the sensitivity study involving standoff distance, all variables except the standoff distance are in accordance with Table 5, while the standoff distance mean value is varied from a reduction of 75% up to an increase of 200%. Figure 16 plots the fractional change in the results versus the fractional change in the mean value for each parameter. As shown in Figure 16, changing the casing diameter causes the largest fluctuation in results. This is attributed to the fact that changing the casing diameter also changes the charge weight of the explosive, as the charge weight is directly calculated from the geometry of the casing. Changing the concrete strength is also observed to have a large effect on the results, with a 75% reduction in concrete strength causing an 80% increase in probability of penetration for a 100mm thick wall.

Figure 16: Sensitivity study plotting the fractional change in probability of perforation of 100 mm wall

4.3 Injury to Personnel

For a given wall thickness and standoff distance, 100,000 samples were used in the Monte Carlo simulation and thus 100,000 fragments with a particular fragment mass and fragment velocity were considered. Each of these samples is plotted against the human critical organ injury thresholds as shown in Figure 17. In the case that the fragment did not penetrate the wall, the fragment velocity is zero. Figure 17 clearly demonstrates how the dispersion of the fragment mass and velocity is much greater than the different thresholds for each critical organ, thus justifying the use of a single threshold curve. Additionally, treating the organ threshold as a stochastic variable would make little difference in the results since the coefficient of variation for each human critical organ injury threshold is very small compared to the dispersion in fragment mass and velocity.

Figure 17: Fragment mass and velocity versus critical organ damage threshold for a mean wall thickness

of 150mm and a mean standoff of 12m

Only injuries occurring from perforation of the wall are considered. Concrete spall from primary fragments generally results in velocities less than 1.5m/s (DoD 2008a), thus spall from fragment penetration alone is unlikely to cause personnel injury. However, when designing a wall system it is important to also consider the blast pressure from the explosive, which can create lethal spall velocities (Naito, Olmati, Trasborg, Davidson, & Newberry 2014).

By taking the quotient of the number of samples that fall in the injury area, referred to as "lethal fragments", and the total number of samples, it is possible to compute the probability of injury occurring. In this paper, it is assumed that lethal fragment generation and injury are directly correlated, i.e. when a lethal fragment occurs injury will also occur. This can then be repeated for multiple wall thicknesses by following the procedure depicted in Figure 11 in order to obtain a pseudo-fragility curve for injury where the wall thickness is the intensity measure.

Figure 18 plots the probability of injury occurring for the standoff distances corresponding to the high, medium, and low threat levels provided in Table 2. The solid lines represent the probability of injury occurring if all fragments strike the wall panel while the dotted lines represent the probability of injury occurring considering fragment trajectory. Intuitively, a thinner wall thickness and closer standoff distance increases the likelihood of injury occurring.

As seen in Figure 18, there exists a possibility that even with an infinitesimally thin wall the personnel subjected to the mortar blast may not be struck by a fragment traveling fast enough or with enough mass to cause injury, thus neither the solid or dotted curves reach a probability of 100%. However, at the standoff distances prescribed in Table 2, the effects of the over pressure developed during the detonation will likely harm a person if no physical barrier is present.

Figure 18: Probability of injury

5 CONCLUSIONS

Probabilistic analyses were conducted in order to design reinforced concrete wall systems against ballistic threats from small arms fire and fragmenting munitions. The study presents an approach for assessing the likelihood of perforation, residual velocity, and life safety of occupants given various design scenarios. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- The approach can be used to develop pseudo-fragility curves for assessing perforation of a concrete wall based on a design threat. The four design levels for direct fire weapons threats from UFC 4-023-07: Very High, High, Medium and Low are used as a basis. Currently, UFC 4-023-07 does not furnish a method for calculating the probability of wall penetration or residual velocity.
- The pseudo-fragility curves for fragment perforation deviate significantly from the confidence level method set forth in UFC 3-340-02. This indicates that the use of stochastic variables to define the fragment threat affects the probability of perforation and spall.
- Pseudo-fragility curves can be developed which account for fragment trajectory, while the confidence level method in UFC 3-340-02 does not differentiate between all fragments generated from the munition and fragments that will actually strike the target.
- The likelihood of injury can be assessed based on critical organ thresholds presented in UFC 3-340-02. The variance in organ tolerance is much smaller than the variance in fragment mass and velocity, justifying the use of a single, deterministic injury threshold for all organs.
- The pseudo-fragility curves for injury can be developed for various threat levels with the wall thickness as the intensity measure to quickly provide the engineer and owner with an understanding of the level of safety of the wall system for the defined threat level.
- The work presented provides a probabilistic framework for assessing the probability of exceeding a given limit state (e.g. design threat, wall thickness, or injury threshold), allowing engineers to develop tools to quickly quantify the safety of a structure under direct and indirect fire weapons' demands.

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